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POLICY BRIEF

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This deliverable outlines the results of the systematic policy-evidence scan on legume production or consumption and ecosystem services carried out within WP5 of the LegumES project. Coupled with insights from initial stakeholder consultations (undertaken through the multi-actor workshops and policy dialogues), the document outlines preliminary policy recommendations that will be further investigated and tested during the reminding project period (in WP 3, 5 and 6).	
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Background to the LegumES project

The LegumES will ensure:

1. the uptake of best practices in agrobiodiverse legume-based cropped systems;
2. the uptake of methodologies and tools to quantify and balance the environmental and economic ecosystem service (ES) benefits provided by legumes;
3. that the ES benefits and cost offered by legumes are quantified across scales from field, farm, regional, national, and global levels; and
4. ES will be assessed to identify those conditions which are able to meet the EU targets: to decrease agrichemical inputs and losses, combat climate change, reverse biodiversity loss, and ensure the best nutritional provisioning.

To achieve this, LegumES offers a multi-disciplinary consortium comprising 22 partners from 12 EU- and third countries (UK, CH) and including: 7, academic institutions; 6, Research and Technology Organizations; 5, SMEs (or micro-SMEs); 2, non-governmental organisations; and 2, large commercial companies. The individuals comprising LegumES offer skills which include: agricultural-crop and -environment (ES) monitoring, life cycle assessment, economic- and socioeconomic-modelling, social-science, EU-agricultural and environmental policy, and law, plus decision support systems. The LegumES research and innovation strategy centres on the use of a multi-actor action-research approach, that is, where legume-facing stakeholders, and especially producers though all value chains actors, can 'operate', 'collaborate' and, reflect critically' on the measured ES benefits and costs of legume-based cropped systems, including legumes use in marginal lands; so that an optimal balance of ES can be achieved with success locally, and globally. To help achieve this, LegumES also centres activities on a suite of 25 innovative legume-based Pilot Studies which use a wide range of legume species and types, plus different cropping approaches and linked value chains spanning the pedoclimatic regions of Europe.

For more information on the project, see:

- [Valorising and balancing the ecosystem service benefits offered by legumes, and legume-based cropped systems | LegumES | Project | Fact sheet | HORIZON | CORDIS | European Commission](#)
- www.legumesproject.eu

Executive Summary

This policy brief outlines findings from a systematic policy-evidence scan and early engagement with stakeholders and experts to understand how policy interventions shape the production and consumption of legumes, and more specifically, the recognition of the delivery of associated ecosystem services (ES). The review shows that the environmental benefits of legumes are broadly acknowledged in EU and national policy frameworks, especially when linked to coupled income support for agricultural production. However, the economic and social dimensions of ES linked to legumes remain insufficiently integrated into policies. Value chain enabling interventions, such as the development of processing capacity, support through contracting mechanisms or advisory services, and demand-side measures targeting the consumption of legumes remain weak. Stakeholder and expert consultation further emphasise the fragmentation and low ambition of policy measures, and a lack of coherence between agricultural, environmental policies on the one hand and dietary or health policies on the other. The emerging policy intervention matrix developed in this report identified areas of convergence but also persistent gaps in policy interventions, especially with regards to the monitoring of ES, the distinction between food or feed purposes in production, and the limited uptake of legume-specific advisory tools. The brief proposes preliminary recommendations to strengthen the alignment of policies that could integrate the recognition of ES provided by legumes production or consumption across scales. These recommendations will be further tested under WP3 and WP6, before their finalisation by the end of the LegumES project.

1. Introduction

Ecosystem services (ES) encompass tangible and intangible advantages (goods and services) that ecosystems offer to society, whether natural or modified by humans (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2003). The characteristics and processes of an ecosystem determine its ability to deliver goods and services to people, referred to as ecosystem functions by de Groot (1992) and de Groot (2006). Legumes-related ES emerge from a complex interaction of agricultural, environmental, market, consumption and nutrition measures across multiple levels of governance. They thereby require the analysis of a 'policy mix' that reflects such complexity and identifies synergies or contradictions between different interventions, acknowledging that any policy development is almost always constrained by institutionalised policy choices (Howler and Rayner, 2007). To map the interaction between measures, the impact pathways associated with each policy intervention need to be identified and thereafter combined with the integration of stakeholder perspectives identified to validate, refine and contextualise findings (Rogers, 2014).

This brief outlines the results of the policy-evidence scanning carried out in relation with policy interventions to increase legumes production and consumption, while also providing the preliminary conclusions of stakeholder feedback gathered through different consultation activities carried out within the LegumES project (through multi-actor workshops and policy dialogues). Developing a policy intervention matrix, it also outlines preliminary policy recommendations that will be further investigated through the Delphi exercise carried out under WP5, and the bottom-up work under WP3.4, leading to the final LegumES policy recommendations by M45, which will integrate all project outputs relevant to policy.

2. Systematic policy-evidence scan on legume production or consumption and ecosystem services

A **structured policy-evidence scan** was carried out to identify policy synergies, gaps and leverage points to enhance the contribution of legumes to sustainable food systems, faced with complex policy problems that need to be addressed through policy instrument mixes (Howler and Rayner, 2007). The policy evidence scanning exercise combined a targeted policy mapping (2.1.) with a systematic literature review (2.2) to capture both the current legislative landscape and recent analytical studies addressing policy measures that influence the production, processing or consumption of legumes and the ecosystem services they deliver, as well as an in-depth review of policy recommendations developed by past research projects (2.3). Each source was systematically coded according to a shared analytical framework to ensure comparability across governance levels, policy instrument types, and targeted stages of the food system, as outlined in the Annex.

2.1. Policy scanning and mapping

As a first step, the policy-evidence scan focused on the **identification and analysis of applicable EU and national policies on the production and consumption of legumes**, including the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), the Zero Pollution Action Plan, the EU Pollinators Initiative, the EU Protein Strategy, the Sustainable Use of Pesticides, and seed marketing regulations, as well as dietary guidelines and public procurement schemes. Complementary examples were drawn from the United

Kingdom’s Environmental Land Management (ELM) scheme, which replaced the CAP and provides a comparative model of agricultural production support and eco-scheme design. The review also integrated the most recent academic and grey literature on ecosystem services provided by legumes, particularly those studies that explicitly examine the role of policy instruments across the food, feed and consumption value chains.

While a clear **concentration of activity was identified at the EU level**, national-level policies from countries including Denmark, Hungary, Cyprus, Czechia, Estonia, Germany and Greece, illustrated how EU frameworks are implemented, adapted, or supplemented domestically. With regards to the **nature of instruments** present in the policy landscape, the mapping identified *binding* instruments (EU Common Agricultural Policy and national CAP Strategic Plans with direct incentives for legume production, EU seed marketing rules), while 6 *non-binding strategies* at EU level alone have been flagged as linking legume production and ecosystem services (such as the European Green Deal and associated strategies such as the Farm to Fork Strategy, or the draft EU Plant Protein Strategy proposed by the European Parliament, or the EU Green Procurement Plan). The policy landscape impacting home-grown legumes also includes a considerable number of *voluntary schemes with mandatory legal provisions* to which operators may choose to opt-in, hoping for premium returns (such as eco-schemes or rural development programmes under the CAP, organic certification, Eco-Management Audit Scheme, protected designation of origin or protected geographical indications).

Figure 1. Typology of EU/UK policy intervention on legumes (including draft strategies).

The scanning highlighted that most of the policy intervention remains **focused on the provision of primary agricultural inputs and agricultural production** in general, while interventions targeting or including provisions or tools to target food/feed processing or consumption are scarcer (Figure 1). The **objectives** of policy interventions differ quite widely, targeting *largely economic considerations* such

as reducing import dependency, supporting farmers' income or local production chains, increasing the marketability or profitability of certain products. *Environmental objectives* also stand out amongst the different policies, ranging from the promotion of 'circularity', including the reduction in the use of pesticides and synthetic nitrogen fertiliser – the latter due soil enrichment via transfer of biologically fixated nitrogen improvement of soil qualities more generally, and so help preserve the wellbeing of the natural environment. *Societal priorities* such as promoting public health, decreasing meat consumption or balancing diets, or protecting traditional and cultural heritage seem to play a more minor role in the EU policy landscape linking ecosystem services and legumes. Protein autonomy and Europe's persistent protein deficit have become central themes in current EU food-security debates.

The emerging EU protein strategy seeks to make protein crops competitive across all farming systems, regions, and production contexts. This agenda traces back to the Commission's *Report on the development of plant proteins in the European Union* (COM (2018) 757 final, 22 November 2018), which set out policy options to boost EU-grown plant proteins. The report focused on protein-rich crops (>15% crude protein) such as oilseeds, pulses and soy, examining their development across three market segments: conventional feed, premium feed, and food. Although food use was described as a "smaller, but potentially considerably profitable" market, amounting to roughly 3 Mt of peas, faba beans, lentils, chickpeas and soy, the primary emphasis remained on addressing the feed protein deficit by increasing EU production, mainly for livestock systems. In 2023, the European Parliament adopted its own-initiative resolution on a *European Protein Strategy* (A9-0281/2023; P9_TA(2023)0375), which significantly widened the scope of the discussion, despite its emphasis on ensuring greater levels of self-sufficiency and reduced import dependency, rather than the ecosystem benefits linked to legumes production and consumption. The resolution moves beyond "plant proteins for feed" to encompass "all proteins across food and feed systems." This broader framing opens political space for debates on diets, alternative proteins and circularity. Still, it also dilutes strategic focus: when almost any protein source becomes part of the agenda, prioritisation becomes more difficult. Despite the heightened political attention, the degree of policy integration remains limited. While CAP rules, research priorities and monitoring tools increasingly reference the protein agenda, structural dependency on imports has barely shifted. EU pulse cultivation and high-protein self-sufficiency have increased only marginally, and large volumes of imported protein, particularly soymeal, continue to dominate the system.

The only policy instrument where a direct link is established between the provision of ecosystem services and legumes is the voluntary scheme of the EU Eco-Management Audit Scheme (EMAS). However, it seems that the success of this audit scheme remains limited in the field of agriculture, and even more so with regards to legumes. Further work undertaken in WP5 will need to explore the reasons behind such timid engagement and explore pathways to further valorise the ecosystem services provided by home-grown legumes.

Unsurprisingly, the major instrument which links ecosystem services and legumes, albeit in an indirect fashion that justifies the existence of the policy intervention as such, remains the EU's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). **The CAP plays an integral and pivotal part in legume production**, cited in all literature studying the nexus between policy, ecosystem services and legumes. Due to its relatively new adoption in 2023, there is a further need to examine the impact and efficiency of the new CAP delivery model, knowing that numerous national CAP Strategic Plans have taken direct or indirect action towards home-grown legumes. **Coupled income support is linked to legumes or protein crops in 20 Member States**, in some cases increasing the financial contribution to coupled support for protein crops and legumes (IE, FR, PL, IT, LV, EL, ES, LT, HU, BG, SK and LU), or introducing new coupled

support for these crops in the case of Wallonia in Belgium, PT, SI and EE. Another CAP tool used by EU Member States is the new **eco-scheme** integrated in the policy's first pillar, with the example of France and its support of plant protein cultivation through the French Recovery and Resilience Plan. It is also noted that policy incentives targeting solely environmental considerations (such as those linked to cover cropping in non-productive areas) may have unintended detrimental consequences with regards to the development of markets and sustainable food value chains for home-grown legumes, or even in terms of land use change.

With the major exception of coupled income support under the CAP, most policy interventions are intended to have an **indirect rather than direct impact** on the production or consumption of legumes, such as those related to non-productive measures under the CAP, or the support of nitrogen fixing crops or alternatives to pesticide use. The true impact of these policies and their efficiency in the recognition of ecosystem services provided by home-grown legumes needs to be further assessed in WP5 activities. Based on systematic policy scanning, both the Delphi surveys and the policy dialogues will thus focus on exploring the intended, expected and measured impacts of policy interventions to recognise and valorise ecosystem services provided by home-grown legumes, looking at trade-offs between different policy interventions, as well as the different dimensions of ecosystem services.

2.2. ES literature review

In a second step, a **targeted search for policy-relevant sources was done in the systematic literature review database developed by WP3 regarding ES** and contained 1,588 items in total. All articles that included references to policy, not only in the keywords and abstract, but also in the article itself, were included in our initial scan, which included 76 articles. These articles were organized and managed through Rayyan, a web and mobile app for systematic reviews. After screening duplicates and relevance, 21 articles were excluded. Criteria for exclusion were based only on whether the topic of legumes had been covered beyond a simple referral, i.e. whether a specific statement, recommendation or interpretation had been discussed for this plant type.

Considering the focus of the articles studied, the following assessment can be made.

- **Country Distribution:** The data includes examples from various regions globally: EU, South America (Amazonia), North America (US), Africa, India, Kazakhstan, UK, Spain, and others. Some regions are heavily over-represented compared to others (EU, India).
- **Legume Species:** Many different legume species are mentioned (soybean, chickpea, pea, lentil, alfalfa, faba bean, clover, pulses, and others), but the studies examined were primarily general in their focus and generally concerned legumes and pulses.
- **Cropping Systems:** Intercropping is a frequently mentioned cropping system, often combined with cereals. Other systems, including sole cropping, crop rotations (including legume-based rotations), double cropping, and multi-cropping systems, are also represented.
- **Value Chain Positions:** The articles deal with various value chain stages: production, processing, marketing, and consumption. Focus across the value chain is uneven, with some segments, like consumption, receiving relatively less detail than production.

The studied papers often mentioned ES benefits related to legumes, summarised in Table 1. The discussed environmental, economic, and socio-cultural benefits are interconnected. For example, improved soil health (environmental) usually leads to increased yields and profitability (economic), which can contribute to improved livelihoods and food security (socio-cultural).

Table 1. Summary of ES attributed to legumes production and consumption

Ecosystem Service Category	Environmental Contributions	Economic Contributions	Socio-Cultural Contributions
Legumes in general	Biological nitrogen fixation (reducing fertiliser use, GHG emissions); improved soil health (structure, organic matter, water retention); biodiversity benefits; pest and disease control; carbon sequestration.	Reduced input costs (synthetic (mineral) nitrogen fertilisers, pesticides); increased yields (often in intercropping systems); improved profitability (depending on market conditions and policy support); improved system productivity.	Improved food security, nutritional benefits (protein, micronutrients), cultural significance (in some regions), and potential for improved livelihoods, especially for smallholder farmers.
Intercropping Systems	Enhanced biodiversity, improved water use efficiency, reduced weed pressure, increased resilience to pests and diseases, and improved soil health.	There is potential for higher yields and profitability, but this can depend on market access, processing infrastructure, and efficient harvesting techniques.	Potential for increased food security, nutritional diversity, and diversified income streams for farmers.

The policy recommendations consistently **emphasise a shift from direct production subsidies for legumes to a holistic, value-chain approach** that fosters enabling conditions for sustainable legume production and consumption. Key themes addressed in the literature include:

- **Market-oriented policies:** Focus on stimulating demand through demand-side policies (e.g., public procurement, labelling, market information), R&D investments in processing technologies, and support for short food supply chains to improve market access and competitiveness for legume products.
- **Sustainable agricultural practices:** Encourage agroecological principles, reduce reliance on synthetic fertilisers, and incentivise practices that deliver positive environmental and health outcomes.
- **Consumer awareness:** Invest in public awareness campaigns and nutritional education to increase legume consumption, align dietary guidelines and consumer preferences with sustainable food systems.
- **Policy integration:** Align agricultural, environmental, and health policies to create synergies across sectors, avoid disconnects between sustainable diets and farming practices, and incentivise the multiple benefits associated with legume cultivation.
- **Research and innovation:** Invest in research and development to improve legume varieties, breeding programmes, cultivation techniques, and processing methods, enhancing productivity, resilience, and adaptability to various environments.
- **Support for farmers:** Provide farmers with financial and technical assistance (training, extension services, advisory services, access to credit and insurance) to facilitate the adoption of sustainable legume-based farming systems and manage associated risks.

The articles studied mention several existing policies that could be leveraged, but details of their impact and articulation are scarce and often given only a brief glimpse of their impact on the production and consumption of legumes, or the recognition of associated ES. Despite this often inconsistent and incomplete information, some key observations can still be drawn from the review.

- **CAP (Common Agricultural Policy):** The CAP is frequently referenced, with certain components (e.g., area payments for grain legumes, environmental conditionality measures) seen as having some, though often limited, positive effects on legume cultivation. However, the CAP's overall impact on legume production is mixed, with some aspects potentially hindering the broader adoption of legumes (e.g., focus on major crops).
- **Agri-environmental schemes:** Various agri-environmental schemes (AES) and related programmes offer potential support for legume-related practices like intercropping and crop diversification. However, the degree and effectiveness of such support vary regionally.
- **Other policies:** National policies, such as land-use policies and those related to food security and health, are noted as influencing legume production, but few specifics on the content or effectiveness of these policies are provided.
- **Regional initiatives:** Certain regions have specific initiatives (e.g., Estonian Agri-environment measures, some policies in India) to promote legume cultivation or integrated farming systems, but broad details about their impact are unavailable.

The recommendations linked to policy in literature focusing on ES associated with legumes call for a **comprehensive, multi-sectoral strategy beyond simply boosting production to build a more resilient and sustainable legume system that benefits producers, consumers, and the environment.** Direct subsidies are generally less effective than fostering enabling conditions across the value chain.

2.3. Research project recommendations review

Last but not least, **policy-related findings and recommendations from previous European Union (EU) funded projects** were identified. A total of 30 projects were screened, of which 9 are still ongoing and therefore their results are not yet available, and 21 projects have already been completed. Among the completed projects, we were able to analyse the policy recommendations developed in a total of 10 related projects (Diverfarming, 2017-2022, DiverImpacts, 2017-2022, Diversify, 2017-2021, Legumes Translated, 2018-2022, LegValue, 2017-2021, LIFT project, 2018-2022, ProLegSo, 2011-2014, Remix, 2017-2021, Suscrop ERANET, 2018-2023 and TRUE, 2017-2021).

The main conclusion regarding legume-related policy suggestions is that a holistic, value-chain approach is needed, focusing on enabling conditions rather than direct production subsidies. This translates into several key policy directions, outlined below in Table 2.

Table 2. Policy directions and supporting actions in legumes-related research projects.

Main Policy Direction	Supporting Actions	Rationale
Enable Market Development	Invest in R&D and processing technologies; utilise demand-side policies (e.g., standardisation, labelling, public procurement); support short supply chains.	Create market pull for high-quality legume products; improve competitiveness; benefit domestic producers.
Promote Sustainable Practices	Encourage agroecological principles; discourage inorganic nitrogen fertilisers; reward positive environmental and health impacts.	Enhance sustainability, improve environmental outcomes, and align with sustainable diets.
Raise Consumer Awareness	Implement nutritional education, dietary guidelines, and public health campaigns.	Increase legume consumption; bridge the gap between sustainable diets and farming practices.

Main Policy Direction	Supporting Actions	Rationale
Foster Collaboration & Knowledge Sharing	Facilitate knowledge transfer; promote cooperation across the value chain.	Improve efficiency, innovation, and implementation of policies and practices.
Integrate Policies	Link agricultural, environmental, and health policies.	Ensure policy coherence and avoid disconnects between sustainable diets and farming incentives.

In short, policy interventions should be **focused on more than simply increasing legume production but on creating a supportive environment across entire value chains**, enhancing sustainability, and stimulating consumer demand. Direct subsidies are less effective than enabling market conditions and fostering broader changes in agricultural practices.

3. Stakeholder views on policy

The literature scan revealed several **important evidence gaps** that limit the development of targeted and effective policy recommendations on ES recognition in legumes production and consumption. Quantified outcomes are often under-reported in literature, with few sources providing robust metrics on yield stability, input reduction, profitability or socio-cultural benefits, despite frequent claims regarding health, rural development or equity impacts. Evidence on consumption-side interventions remains particularly thin. Beyond food-based dietary guidelines and a handful of national plans, there is limited evaluation of public procurement measures, retail or catering nudges, VAT adjustments, labelling initiatives or school food schemes that specifically target legumes. The limited distinction between legumes production for feed or food is also a barrier to the comprehensive assessment of policy intervention impact, as many instruments aggregate all “protein crops,” obscuring the specific needs and impacts of edible pulses on the overall food system and different ES linked to legumes, especially with regards to their consumption.

2.4. Insights from multi-actor workshops (MAWs)

National Multi-actor Workshops (MAWs) coordinated under WP1 invited **key stakeholders and actors in legume value chains, from production and processing to retail, research, and policy at a national level**. MAWs brought together existing communities and industrial networks involved in legumes, building on previous related projects and existing relationships/networks. The workshops were organised by each LegumES project-partner country throughout 2024 and 2025, and asked legume stakeholder’s the question: *What do you perceive to be the important benefits of legumes in agriculture and diets and how can we increase the value of these benefits in agri-food systems and society?*

By working with stakeholders to co-create knowledge about the ecosystem benefits of legume production and consumption, these workshops aimed to understand how legumes could be integrated into national agri-food systems through existing or novel schemes, interventions or incentives. The more detailed objectives pursued by the workshops were to prioritise stakeholders’ goals for legume production, and legume-associated ES valorisation, conceive future scenarios for legume use that optimise opportunities for such valorisation, and finally, to bring together key/influential stakeholders to guide the Theory of Change approach and help develop project legacy.

Our analysis of workshop outputs focused specifically on the **policy-relevant discussions of the WP1 MAWs**, examining how stakeholders perceived the opportunities and constraints shaping the role of legumes in food and farming systems. Findings relevant to policy were identified and evaluated from the following countries: Denmark, France, Hungary, Italy, Macedonia, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain, the UK. Workshops outlined various **factors, supports, and challenges across European countries related to the production, consumption, and policy surrounding legumes**. Participants frequently situated these issues within broader debates on dietary transitions and environmental objectives, while consistently emphasising the need for more robust, coherent and supportive policies.

- **Agricultural Policies:** Lack of support from agricultural policies is a frequently selected high-impact factor in Portugal. Stability and ambition of these policies are highlighted in Slovenia, and fluctuations in agricultural aid are a concern in France.
- **GHG Emissions:** France's National Low Carbon Strategy (SNBC) is relevant for the reduction of Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions, though there is a risk of political and regulatory backtracking (weakening of the SNBC) in a global context where economic and security issues are resurfacing,
- **Soil Health:** Soil C sequestration was mentioned in Spain, and indirect producer support through soil health improvement was noted in Hungary.
- **Supply Chains:** There is a possibility to create coherent value chains, which place the primary producer in a less dependent position economically. Also, issues like high investment costs of processing infrastructure and potential job losses in existing supply chains if shortening supply chains were mentioned in the UK.
- **Consumption Support:**
 - The food service sector can act as leverage to increase both consumption and production of legumes.
 - Introducing societal educational programmes and campaigns to stimulate consumption was a frequently selected high importance factor in several countries.
 - Inclusion in consumption guidelines and the need for a reduced value added tax (VAT) was noted as a potential solution in Hungary.
 - School food legislation (collaborating with municipalities) was mentioned in Portugal.
- **Financial Support/Incentives:**
 - Subsidies could mitigate the higher cost of Danish-produced legumes compared to imported ones, facilitating local purchases (e.g., in public canteens).
 - Hungarian participants mentioned direct producer support and indirect support through soil health improvement and increased agrobiodiversity.
 - Availability of subsidies for ecosystem services was mentioned in Slovenia.
 - In the UK, the existing Sustainable Farm Incentive (SFI) was seen as a potential economic service/benefit. However, a weakness identified was that existing environmental schemes might be compromised and that there are complexities in fitting incentives within current schemes and land ownership arrangements.
- **Political Push:** The benefits of home-grown legumes (e.g., self-sufficiency in times of crises) can act as a "political push" to drive a transition towards a more plant-based diet.
- **Regulatory/Lobbying:**
 - Macedonia notes a regulation for growing legumes on 10% of the soil.
 - An "agriculture-lobby" could promote the benefits of legumes to increase production interest was mentioned in Denmark.
 - Lobby for animal protein was mentioned in Portugal.

- Administrative constraints and overload were mentioned as risks/threats in France related to nitrogen input service.
- The need for legislation to protect local legume production to mitigate competition from global markets and geopolitical events was a proposed action in the UK.

2.5. Policy dialogues

To receive more detailed feedback on the role of policy intervention in the recognition of ES provided by legumes production and consumption, WP5 organised a **survey-based policy dialogue in selected countries**. Policy-relevant actors and experts in EU countries where partners operate have been involved in policy dialogues on the nation-state level/regional/local levels of authority to better understand views regarding ES benefits provided by legumes.

The policy dialogues helped further **investigate stakeholder views and perceived impacts of the development of new policies and regulations on the uptake of home-grown legumes and the recognition or valorisation of ecosystem services provided by legume production and consumption**. They addressed all policies defined in the mapping (2.1), covering those related to consumer, producer, market, food/feed environment and horizontal policies, including relevant European strategies. The objectives of the dialogues were to: (a) gather expert views on implementing home-grown legume policies by identifying local/regional specificities and looking into the impacts of such policies on legume production, transformation and consumption; (b) address ES trade-offs in legume-focused policy instruments at local and regional levels; and (c) identify questions/statements for the Delphi study that will be carried out to develop and validate policy recommendations.

Information was collected through a short online questionnaire containing mainly open questions. The forms were distributed in Hungary, Portugal and the UK. The sample consists of 8 respondents from the UK (including England, Scotland and Northern Ireland), 13 respondents from Portugal and 10 respondents from Hungary.

Across the UK, Portugal, and Hungary, there is growing recognition of the benefits of home-grown legumes, but **policy frameworks remain fragmented, narrow in scope, and weakly implemented**. While environmental aspects (like biological nitrogen fixation) receive some attention, economic and social dimensions are underrepresented. Experts across the 3 countries call for integrated, systemic, and market-supported approaches to make legumes a viable and sustainable part of national food systems.

Regarding **awareness and policy effectiveness**, policies are perceived as tokenistic, lacking ambition, clear targets, and sufficient financial backing. The CAP, ELM, and SFI are acknowledged but criticised for vagueness, bureaucracy, and low incentives. Legume policies fail to shift mainstream practices and reduce the risk burden on farmers.

The **recognition of benefits stemming from legume production** mainly focuses on environmental benefits (soil improvement, biological nitrogen fixation), which are the most recognised and supported in policy interventions. Economic benefits (cost savings, local value chains) are partially acknowledged but not well incentivised, while social and cultural benefits (nutrition, public health, heritage diets) are largely overlooked. Experts call for food-system-level coherence, linking the environment, economy, and society. The prioritisation of benefits is similar across the three involved countries: environmental > economic > social in perceived importance. Respondents emphasise the interconnectedness of these benefits and advocate for holistic, cross-sectoral policy design. Financial viability for farmers is seen as a prerequisite for wider adoption, which means that the weaknesses of valorising ecosystem services of legumes are mainly economic.

The policy dialogues also looked in **more detail into existing policy interventions**, attempting to identify their perceived strengths and weaknesses. The agricultural support mechanisms and schemes (CAP/ELM) are seen as insufficient or too early to assess. The following criticisms are most common: 1) low payment rates, 2) bureaucratic complexity, 3) weak market and demand-side support. Experts urge the adoption of joined-up strategies that connect production, supply chains, and consumption. The value chain coverage of legumes-related policies is seen as inadequate, as they mainly target producers, neglecting other key actors (processors, retailers, consumers). In the UK, experts recognise a broader actor network (including retailers and public catering), but implementation gaps persist. In Portugal and Hungary, the focus is mainly on farmers, thus missing opportunities to engage processors or consumers. Local interventions are minimal or fragmented according to respondents from all three countries. They agree that local-level integration — via public procurement, regional markets, or education — is crucial but underdeveloped. Experts from Portugal mentioned isolated good practices, while respondents from Hungary reported no notable local initiatives.

There is a strong consensus on the need for systematic monitoring of legume-related ecosystem services. A proper monitoring system should be outcome-based, farm-led, low-cost, and should cover soil health, biodiversity, GHG emissions, productivity, and public health indicators.

Key takeaways from the policy dialogue are:

- Legume policies are underperforming. Environmental gains are acknowledged, but economic and social levers remain weak.
- Implementation barriers — bureaucracy, poor coordination, and low incentives — persist across countries.
- A systemic approach is needed: connecting agriculture, markets, consumer behaviour, and education.
- Consumer awareness and demand creation are crucial for long-term success.
- Future progress requires multi-actor engagement, better local integration, and robust monitoring frameworks.
- Local policy support would be needed, but it is either lacking or severely limited. Local recognition of the benefits of legumes would be crucial.

3. Policy Intervention Impact Matrix

Drawing on the systematic evidence from the policy scan and preliminary stakeholder insights gathered within the LegumES project, a number of clear convergence points and tensions or gaps emerge across EU and national policy interventions targeting legume production, processing, consumption and attached ES.

4.1. Convergences identified in policy interventions

Recognition of multi-benefit potential of legumes in food systems by policies in the EU and UK

Many policy interventions acknowledge (explicitly or implicitly) the multiple environmental, economic, and social benefits that legumes can deliver to feed and food systems. The presence of overlapping objectives across a significant share of instruments (Figure 2) is itself a recognition of this multifunctionality. However, these overlapping aims also highlight the need to navigate potential trade-offs between ES benefits and agronomic, labour, or land-use considerations.

Figure 2. Overlaps between policy objectives cluster (from policy scanning 2.1, n=21).

Robust evidence and policy support for environmental benefits of legumes production

Environmental objectives are the most consistently included across legislative and strategic documents. Numerous sources find that legume-inclusive systems enhance soil functions, biological nitrogen fixation, biodiversity, and reduce pesticide needs, aligning well with CAP environmental objectives and eco-schemes for biological nitrogen fixation (legume crops), and the European Green Deal (Reckling et al 2013, Ditzler et al., 2021, Gallardo et al, 2022).

Economic potential linked to diversification and value chains

Policy documents and previous projects converge on the finding that legumes can contribute to farm profitability, especially via reduced input needs and diversification benefits (European Commission, 2018, CAP Strategic Plans CY, CZ, EE). However, the economic benefits of legumes expansion are consistently flagged as being conditional to functioning value chains, from processing, contracting, to market access, and predictable demand (Notz et al, 2022). EU strategic documents further link these gains to potential reduced import dependency and the development of regional protein supply chains (European Commission, 2019, EPRS, 2023).

Complementarity between production-side instruments and consumption-side ambitions

Although less developed, dietary guidelines, EU school schemes, national plant-based plans, and health-focused recommendations acknowledge the role of increased pulse consumption in sustainable diets (Food-Based Dietary Guidelines (FBDG) for legumes, 2025, Danish Action Plan for Plant-based Foods, 2023). This complements production-side measures by potentially increasing demand for edible legumes. Public procurement stands out as a lever offering direct, predictable demand, but remains largely under-used by legislators (Health promotion knowledge gateway, 2025).

Strategic policy alignment at EU or national levels steer towards ES recognition

Several high-level EU strategies (e.g. Soil Strategy for 2030, Zero Pollution Action Plan) indirectly encourage legume cultivation, particularly via objectives on soil health, reduced inputs, and diversified rotations. For instance, the Soil Strategy for 2030 and the Zero Pollution action plan may both create indirect demand for rotations with legumes (soil cover, reduced inputs), which dovetails with CAP eco-schemes and GAEC conditionality. While this “strategic coherence” provides a favourable framing, it has not consistently translated into practical coherence in policy design or implementation across the value chain.

4.2. Tensions and gaps

Despite overarching EU strategic alignment on environmental and dietary objectives, practical coherence across agricultural, environmental, and food policies remains limited.

Voluntary/non-binding strategies set high policy ambitions but rarely guarantee uptake or change of practices, as they signal direction but do not guarantee market or farm-level change without price/contracting/processing measures. This contrasts with the binding leverage of CAP conditionality and eco-schemes, which therefore takes centre stage in all legumes related policy actions. Strategies such as the draft Protein Strategy, Green Deal, or dietary guidelines articulate ambitions but lack enforcement or economic incentives (EPRS, 2018). Without strong demand-side or value-chain measures, these instruments often fail to catalyse significant behavioural change at farm or market level.

Market, processing and logistics gaps constrain policy impact.

Across the literature and stakeholder feedback, a recurring barrier is insufficient processing capacity, inconsistent contracting mechanisms, and thin markets (Notz et al, 2022, European Commission, 2019). Without interventions to strengthen these enabling conditions, production-focused measures risk overpromising and underperforming the goals they have set.

Gaps in legume crop breeding programming.

Europe's high import rate for legumes underscores the critical need for locally adapted and high performing legume crop varieties. The limited seed/variety availability for most farmers can undermine efforts to boost agricultural resilience and productivity. Achieving large-scale deployment of a new crop variety necessitates a sustained, multi-decade commitment, involving time needed for successful genetic breeding, the subsequent phase of producing sufficient commercial seed stock, and the eventual period of farmer adoption across various regions (Pardey et al. 2025). Without extensive breeding research funding, an affordable and sustainable food supply that builds on the benefits of legumes cannot be guaranteed. Such funding should be considered in light of the current challenges that exist in legislation aimed to grant intellectual property rights on new plant varieties on the one hand, and agricultural policy, including instruments governing seed market access on the other (Mariani, 2021), especially considering the detrimental effects that regulation of species under seed marketing laws could have on the availability and diversity of plant reproductive material in under-developed markets (Winge, 2015).

Lack of legumes or species-specific policy or advisory guidance.

Most sources default to 'all legumes' or 'protein crops'; species-specific recommendations remain weak to better guide producers or processors. Legumes-specific advice is not sufficiently integrated in the Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS). Many Member States may use their AKIS broadly for new crops/rotation advice, but legume-specific packages (variety choice, seed systems for legumes, legume value-chain processing, market integration) are rarely fully described (ModernAKIS, 2023). There is also little publicly available evaluation of how effective the AKIS measures have been in increasing legume area, productivity, or value-chain development.

Food vs. feed orientation remains largely unaddressed.

Several CAP eco-schemes and national measures privilege nitrogen-fixing cover or forage legumes to deliver environmental outcomes (CAP eco-schemes in HU and DK amongst others), which is beneficial but does not automatically increase the availability of edible pulses for human diets. This can dilute

the link between sustainability goals and human consumption targets from FBDG or national plant-based plans.

Under-reporting and weak monitoring framework of ES.

Most policy documents and evaluations lack quantified metrics on yield stability, input reduction, profitability, or socio-cultural outcomes. This limits opportunities to assess effectiveness, refine measures, or link ES delivery to payment schemes. The lack of such data is a key barrier to evidence-based policymaking. General agri-environmental scheme literature warns that outcomes can be modest or heterogeneous without targeting/monitoring, a caution against assuming strong impacts from eco-schemes alone (Wuepper, 2024).

4.3. Draft recommendations

Table 3. Policy intervention impact review.

What to do?	Why it helps?	Example
Tie policy intervention, especially eco-schemes to edible-pulse outcomes (distinction between legumes production for feed and for human consumption)	Aligns environmental payments with human-food pulses; improves monitoring	Eco-scheme criteria + reporting distinguish edible vs feed indicators
Mandate pulse servings in public procurement to build value chains and increase consumption of home-grown legumes	Creates predictable demand and normalises consumption	School/hospital standards regional sourcing clauses
Fund processing capacity and offtake contracts	Unlocks value chain bottlenecks and reduces price/market risk	Grants/tax credits for dehulling & pre-cooking contract-farming facilitation
Species- & region-specific trials with advisory services and innovation support packages (AKIS)	Improves yield stability and agronomy; provides faster adoption	EAFRD pilots, advisory modules and demonstration farms (LLs)
Introduce risk tools/insurance tailored to legumes	Buffers yield variability and income risk	Crop insurance add-ons - income stabilisation tools
Fiscal reductions & menu nudges for pulses	Boosts affordability and default dietary choices	Reduced VAT on specific legumes products (dried/canned pulses); default vegetarian options in canteens with emphasis on plant protein intake
Clarify trade requirements and standards to support the production and consumption of EU legumes	Improves competitiveness and resilience	Monitor TRQs; align import standards; origin labelling

5. Conclusions and next steps

Both the policy-evidence scan, and stakeholder inputs highlight that **legume-related policy incentives remain fragmented and have only limited social or market integration components**. There is a systemic gap between strong agricultural policy incentives (CAP, ELM) for production, and broader food system strategies (procurement, education, nutrition). Stakeholders also express readiness for cross-sectoral policy innovation, particularly at local and regional levels, where legumes could link biodiversity and food goals.

To test and validate the policy intervention impact matrix and the policy recommendations contained therein, targeted consultations with stakeholders will be carried out. Experts will be consulted more in depth through a Delphi study (Balazs et al. 2021), which aims to understand perspectives on: (1) the impact of the incentives/instruments that are currently available; and (2) what else is required to support the wider production and use of homegrown, locally adapted legumes. Through two rounds, each lasting 15-20 minutes for respondents, legume-based incentives/policy instruments, as well as the trade-offs associated with legumes, will be assessed. The first wave of this study commenced in mid-October 2025; the second wave is scheduled to begin in December/January 2026. In addition, the policy intervention matrix and accompanying draft recommendations will be used in the WP3 workshops for farm-level evaluation of policy interventions using AgriToolKit, as well as the impact assessment of legumes focused policy intervention on markets.

Policy recommendations will be further developed and refined based on such stakeholder input, as well as in-depth case studies of policy interventions at regional or national level that stand out through their integration of ES associated to legumes, especially in relation to their social dimensions.

6. Annex: Methodological considerations for systematic policy-evidence scan

Policy scanning and mapping exercise.

The legal scan identified 42 relevant entries, consisting of 21 legislative or strategic policy texts and 21 scholarly or practice-oriented sources linked to a policy instrument through Boolean searches on Eurlex, Scopus, Google Scholar and Zenodo.

The review categorised each source by the nature of the policy tool under examination. This involved distinguishing between binding instruments, such as the CAP Strategic Plans Regulation, conditionality rules (GAEC standards), and eco-schemes, and voluntary or non-binding measures, including protein strategy briefings, dietary guidelines, national action plans, and other soft-law or advisory instruments. Sources were also classified according to their policy target area. This spanned beyond primary production to include interventions affecting agricultural inputs, processing and manufacturing capacity, trade and value-chain coordination, and consumption or dietary behaviour. This whole-chain lens made it possible to assess how policies interact across different stages of the food and feed system.

The objectives and measured or foreseen outcomes of each policy intervention documented in each source were thereafter clustered into three recurrent category of ES, stemming from environmental and climate aims (such as improving soil fertility, enhancing biodiversity, and increasing nitrogen-use efficiency), to economic and market considerations (including reducing import dependency, improving farm profitability, and strengthening regional supply chains and logistics), to finally look into incorporated social and consumption goals (such as the promoting healthier diets, improving sustainability in public catering, and supporting food education).

Each intervention was further classified by its expected impact pathway, distinguishing between direct pathways—such as crop-specific payments, eco-schemes dedicated to nitrogen-fixing crops, or pulse-focused public procurement—and indirect pathways, including soil or climate strategies, research and innovation programmes, and market development tools. Indirect pathways were the most frequently observed, indicating that many interventions influence legumes through broader enabling frameworks rather than dedicated, legume-specific measures.

ES literature review

A targeted search for policy-relevant sources was done in the systematic literature review database developed by WP 3. The table on which the analysis is based and compiled by WP3 contained 1588 items, which we searched using the ‘policy’ keyword. All articles that included the policy topic not only in the keywords and abstract, but also in the article itself, were included in our initial database, which contained 76 articles. These articles were organized and managed through Rayyan, a web and mobile app for systematic reviews. After screening for duplicates and relevance, 20 articles were excluded. Criteria for exclusion were based only on whether the legume topic had been covered beyond the mention, i.e. whether a specific policy-related statement, recommendation or interpretation had been discussed for these plants.

Research project recommendations review.

A total of 30 projects were evaluated, 9 of which are still ongoing and therefore have no results, while 21 projects are already closed. Of the closed projects, 11 had no documents to evaluate, so we analysed the policy recommendations of a total of 10 related projects, as follows:

- Diverfarming, 2017-2022
- DiverImpacts, 2017-2022
- Diversify, 2017-2021
- Legumes Translated, 2018-2022
- LegValue, 2017-2021
- LIFT project, 2018-2022
- ProLegSo, 2011-2014
- Remix, 2017-2021
- Suscrop ERANET, 2018-2023
- TRUE, 2017-2021

7. References**Legislative sources (including non-binding texts)**

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- CAP Eco-scheme, Hungary
- CAP Strategic Plan, Cyprus, https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/document/download/bc01e09b-946e-4b79-8040-bb0835887147_en?filename=csp-at-a-glance-cyprus_en.pdf
- CAP Strategic Plan, Czechia, https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/document/download/ccf0c6e9-53ec-4ef0-8769-dd58baecfc72_en?filename=csp-at-a-glance-czechia_en.pdf
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- CAP Eco-scheme, France
- CAP Eco-scheme, Denmark
- UK (England) Environmental Land Management Scheme, <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/environmental-land-management-update-how-government-will-pay-for-land-based-environment-and-climate-goods-and-services/environmental-land-management-elm-update-how-government-will-pay-for-land-based-environment-and-climate-goods-and-services#arable-land>
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